

Does Bank Soundness Matter for Firm Value? A Comprehensive Study Using Indonesia's RGEC Evaluation Model

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to examine the effect of bank soundness, measured using the Risk Profile, Good Corporate Governance, Earnings, and Capital (RGEC) framework, on the firm value of conventional banks. Firm value is proxied by Tobin's Q, while bank soundness is measured by non-performing loans (NPL) as a proxy for risk profile, self-assessment scores as a proxy for good corporate governance, return on assets (ROA) as a proxy for earnings, and the capital adequacy ratio (CAR) as a proxy for capital. This research employs descriptive and verificative methods with a quantitative approach. Data analysis is conducted using panel data regression. The sample is selected through purposive sampling, resulting in 42 conventional banks listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange during the 2020–2023 period. Hypothesis testing is performed using the F-test and t-test. The results indicate that the risk profile proxied by NPL has a significant negative effect on firm value. Good corporate governance proxied by self-assessment shows no significant effect on firm value. Earnings proxied by ROA have a significant negative effect on firm value, while capital proxied by CAR has a significant positive effect on firm value. The adjusted R-squared value of 0.164 suggests that 16.4% of the variation in firm value can be explained by risk profile, good corporate governance, earnings, and capital, while the remaining 83.6% is influenced by other factors outside the research model.

KEYWORDS: Risk Profile, Good Corporate Governance, Return on Assets, Capital Adequacy Ratio, Tobin's Q

I. INTRODUCTION

The banking sector plays a strategic role in maintaining financial system stability and supporting a country's economic growth. As financial intermediaries, banks mobilize funds from the public and redistribute them through various forms of financing. The stability of banking performance is therefore crucial, particularly given Indonesia's high reliance on a bank-based financial system. Consequently, bank soundness assessment serves as a fundamental instrument for regulators to ensure that banks conduct their operational activities in a safe, efficient, and sustainable manner.

In Indonesia, bank soundness evaluation currently refers to the RGEC framework (Risk Profile, Good Corporate Governance, Earnings, and Capital), as stipulated in Bank Indonesia Regulation No. 13/1/PBI/2011. The RGEC approach provides a comprehensive assessment of a bank's ability to manage risk, implement effective corporate governance, generate profitability, and maintain adequate

capital. From a theoretical perspective, banks with a high level of soundness are expected to preserve public confidence, attract investors, and ultimately enhance firm value in the capital market. Firm value is a critical indicator as it reflects investors' perceptions of a bank's future prospects, profitability, and risk profile. Based on data obtained from the Financial Services Authority (OJK) Annual Reports, the average soundness level of conventional banks in Indonesia during the observation period generally remained in a healthy condition, with several indicators exhibiting an upward trend, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Nevertheless, bank soundness as assessed internally through financial indicators is not always fully reflected in firm value in the capital market. Firm value, particularly when measured using market-based indicators such as Tobin's Q, represents investors' perceptions of a bank's future prospects, performance, and risk. In practice, there are instances in which banks with relatively strong fundamental soundness

do not necessarily experience an increase in their market value (Figure 2). This condition indicates the potential existence of a gap between banks’ internal performance and the response of the capital market.

Figure 1. Soundness Level of Conventional Banks in Indonesia for the 2020–2023 Period

Source: OJK Annual Reports, Indonesian Banking Statistics 2020–2023

The 2020–2023 period represents a critical phase for the Indonesian banking industry, characterized by economic pressures resulting from the COVID-19 pandemic, post-pandemic economic recovery, and dynamic monetary policy conditions that affected the financial sector. During this period, although the overall soundness of conventional banks showed improvement particularly in terms of capital adequacy, asset quality, and profitability, banking stock price movements on the Indonesia Stock Exchange did not consistently reflect these fundamental conditions. Fluctuations in the market value of banking stocks suggest that investors do not rely solely on financial performance, but also take into account risk factors, governance quality, and market perceptions of bank stability.

Figure 2. Firm Value Based on Tobin’s Q of Conventional Banks for the 2020–2023 Period

Source: Processed data, 2024.

The Risk Profile, Good Corporate Governance, Earnings, and Capital (RGEC) framework is a comprehensive

approach employed by the Financial Services Authority to assess bank soundness. While this framework is designed to evaluate banks’ operational viability and sustainability, the extent to which each RGEC component influences firm value in the capital market remains an empirically relevant issue. Differences in perception between regulators and investors regarding bank performance may lead to misalignment between bank soundness levels and market valuation. In practice, a sound bank condition does not necessarily translate into higher firm value. There are cases in which banks classified as sound based on RGEC assessments do not experience improved market performance, as reflected by stagnant or declining Tobin’s Q values. Conversely, some banks with less favorable RGEC scores may exhibit high firm value due to external factors such as aggressive expansion strategies, reputation, dividend policies, or market sentiment. This discrepancy between internal soundness indicators and market responses constitutes an important issue in evaluating the effectiveness of RGEC as a predictor of firm value.

A number of previous studies have reported mixed findings regarding the relationship between bank soundness and firm value. Several studies suggest that risk profile, good corporate governance, and profitability have a significant influence on firm value (Adyaksana et al., 2024; Apriyanti et al., 2023; Prabawati et al., 2021). In contrast, other studies find that RGEC variables have no significant effect on firm value or only exhibit partial effects (Salsabila et al., 2024; Haq et al., 2020; Aprilia & Hapsari, 2021; Ilham et al., 2020; Ristiani & Santoso, 2018). These divergent findings indicate the existence of a research gap concerning the extent to which the RGEC framework can explain variations in firm value, particularly in the context of Indonesian banking amid the new economic dynamics following the COVID-19 pandemic.

Moreover, during the 2020–2023 period, the banking sector not only experienced substantial pressure due to the pandemic followed by economic recovery, but also faced profound digital transformation and significant changes in the competitive structure of the financial services industry. This environment contributed to heightened volatility in both banks’ financial performance and market valuation. Accordingly, it becomes increasingly relevant to re-examine the relationship between banks’ fundamental conditions as measured by the RGEC framework and firm value, especially for conventional banks listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX), which serves as a key barometer of investor response.

These phenomena provide the underlying rationale for revisiting this research, namely to assess whether bank soundness as measured by the RGEC method is truly reflected in the firm value of conventional banks in Indonesia. This study is expected to offer empirical evidence and a more comprehensive understanding of the relationship

between bank soundness and market value formation, as well as to serve as a reference for regulators, bank management, and investors in evaluating the effectiveness of RGEC implementation as a relevant soundness indicator in investment decision-making.

Based on the foregoing discussion, this study aims to analyze whether the RGEC framework influences firm value in Indonesian conventional banks during the 2020–2023 observation period, with firm value measured using the Tobin’s Q approach.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Risk Profile

Risk profile reflects an assessment of inherent risks and the quality of risk management implementation in bank operations, encompassing eight types of risk: credit, market, liquidity, operational, legal, strategic, compliance, and reputational risks. In this study, risk profile is measured by credit risk using the non-performing loan (NPL) ratio as a proxy. According to Anisa & Suryandari (2021), credit risk as measured by NPL represents the proportion of problem loans, classified as substandard, doubtful, and loss loans relative to total loans extended. A higher NPL ratio is associated with a more adverse impact on firm value (Anam et al., 2022). An increase in non-performing loans may deteriorate credit quality, disrupt banks’ operational performance, and weaken investor confidence, which ultimately leads to a decline in firm value. Bank Indonesia stipulates that a healthy NPL level should remain below 5% (Aprilia & Hapsari, 2021). Based on this rationale, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H1: Risk profile, proxied by non-performing loans, has a significant negative effect on firm value.

B. Good Corporate Governance (GCG)

Good corporate governance (GCG) represents a system of sound governance designed to ensure that a company’s operations are conducted effectively and efficiently. In the banking sector, GCG assessment is carried out through a self-assessment mechanism covering eleven aspects, as stipulated in Bank Indonesia Circular Letter No. 15/15/DPNP/2013. A strong GCG assessment provides a positive signal that the firm is well managed, faces a lower risk of managerial misconduct, and possesses favorable business prospects. In the GCG scoring system, a lower score indicates better governance quality, reflecting effective implementation of GCG principles. Such conditions may enhance investor confidence and increase demand for the bank’s shares, thereby improving firm value (Aprilia & Hapsari, 2021). Empirical evidence from Ristiani & Santoso (2018) shows that GCG, as measured by self-assessment, has a significant negative effect on firm value, implying that the lower the GCG score, the better the bank’s condition, which signals effective governance practices,

attracts investors, and ultimately raises firm value. Based on this discussion, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H2: Good corporate governance, proxied by self assessment, has a significant negative effect on firm value.

C. Earnings

Earnings constitute a key indicator in assessing a bank’s ability to generate profits and reflect the effectiveness of management in overseeing operational activities. According to Bank Indonesia Circular Letter No. 13/24/DPNP/2011, one of the indicators used to evaluate profitability is return on assets (ROA), which measures a bank’s ability to generate earnings from the assets it controls. A higher ROA indicates more efficient asset utilization and stronger financial performance, thereby providing a positive signal to investors, encouraging higher stock prices, and ultimately enhancing firm value (Aprilia & Hapsari, 2021). Bank Indonesia sets an ROA level of 1.5% as a benchmark for good performance (Ristiani & Santoso, 2018).

Several empirical studies report that earnings proxied by ROA have a positive and significant effect on firm value (Prabawati et al., 2021; Ristiani & Santoso, 2018). This finding is consistent with Salsabila et al. (2024), who argue that an increase in ROA reflects higher profitability and more efficient asset management, which attracts investors through the potential returns associated with share ownership and drives an increase in firm value. Accordingly, a higher ROA is associated with greater firm value as reflected in more favorable investor perceptions. Based on this discussion, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H3: Earnings, proxied by return on assets, have a significant positive effect on firm value.

D. Capital

Capital reflects the level of a bank’s capital adequacy in absorbing potential losses and maintaining operational stability, which is commonly measured using the capital adequacy ratio (CAR). A higher CAR indicates a stronger capacity to withstand credit risk and potential losses, thereby sending a positive signal to investors, encouraging greater investment, and ultimately enhancing firm value (Aprilia & Hapsari, 2021). CAR is also considered an important determinant of firm value as it demonstrates that a bank possesses sufficient capital to absorb asset value deterioration and support sustainable profit generation (Prabawati et al., 2021). In accordance with regulations issued by the Financial Services Authority (OJK), banks are required to maintain a minimum capital adequacy ratio of 8% (Aprilia & Hapsari, 2021).

A number of empirical studies document that capital, proxied by CAR, has a positive and significant effect on firm value (Adyaksana et al., 2024; Apriyanti et al., 2023; Prabawati et al., 2021). This evidence is consistent with Anisa & Suryandari (2021), who argue that higher CAR levels signal stronger bank prospects and a lower probability

of financial distress, thereby enhancing investor confidence and firm value. From a theoretical perspective, a higher CAR is expected to exert a more favorable influence on firm value, as it reflects the bank’s ability to manage credit risk and absorb potential losses, which strengthens investor trust and promotes increased investment. Based on the foregoing discussion, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H4: Capital, proxied by the capital adequacy ratio, has a significant positive effect on firm value.

E. Firm Value

Firm value represents investors’ perceptions of a company’s success in managing its resources, which is reflected in its stock price (Aprilia & Hapsari, 2021). A higher stock price corresponds to a higher firm value, whereas a decline in stock price leads to a reduction in firm value. High firm value serves as a crucial indicator for investors, as it reflects how the market evaluates a company’s performance and prospects (Agustina & Bondan, 2018). In this study, firm value is proxied by Tobin’s Q. According to Apriyanti et al. (2023), Tobin’s Q is regarded as one of the most informative measures of firm value because it incorporates all components of capital structure, including both equity and debt, rather than focusing solely on common equity.

Tobin’s Q is an indicator that measures firm value based on both tangible and intangible assets, and reflects the effectiveness and efficiency with which a firm utilizes all of its asset-based resources (Dzahabiyya et al., 2020). Tobin’s Q is calculated by comparing the total market value of a firm to the total book value of its liabilities relative to the total book value of assets. In other words, Tobin’s Q represents firm value as the sum of the market capitalization of equity and the book value of debt (both short-term and long-term liabilities), divided by total assets, which consist of the book value of equity plus the book value of debt (Mediyanti et al., 2021).

III. METHOD

This study employs a quantitative research design. The data used are secondary data in the form of time series and cross-sectional data. Secondary data refer to data collected indirectly from the original sources and are generally compiled by authorized institutions and made publicly available to data users. The data sources for this study include publications from the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX), Bank Indonesia (BI), and the Financial Services Authority (OJK) over the 2020–2023 period. The data analysis technique applied in this research is quantitative data analysis using panel data regression.

The population of this study consists of all conventional banks listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange during the 2020–2023 period. Sample selection is conducted using purposive sampling in order to obtain a representative sample that meets predetermined criteria. Based on these

criteria, a total of 42 conventional banks are selected as the research sample.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Regression Analysis

Table 1 presents the results of the panel data regression estimations for each research variable. The panel data regression method is employed to estimate the coefficients of the linear equation involving one or more independent variables, thereby empirically explaining the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable.

Tabel 1. Panel Regression Result

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	1.658757	0.986101	1.682137	0.0945
NPL	-0.181005	0.081321	-2.225827	0.0274
GCG	-0.221130	0.481764	-0.459000	0.6468
ROA	-0.247509	0.067283	-3.678610	0.0003
CAR	0.028127	0.005985	4.699543	0.0000

Dependent Variable: Tobin’s Q

The regression equation resulting from the panel data regression results in Table 1 is as follows:

$$\text{Tobin's Q} = 1.6588 - 0.1810 \cdot \text{NPL} - 0.2211 \cdot \text{GCG} - 0.2475 \cdot \text{ROA} + 0.0281 \cdot \text{CAR} + 0.9861$$

The coefficients in the regression equation above can be explained as follows:

1. The constant value 1.6588 of indicates that if the three independent variables (NPL, GCG, ROA, and CAR) are constant (zero) and unchanged, the dependent variable, the Tobin’Q, will be 1.6588 units.
2. The value of NPL has a regression coefficient of 0.1810. This means that if the NPL value increases by one unit and the other independent variables remain constant, the NPL ratio is predicted to decrease by 0.1810 units.
3. The value of GCG has a regression coefficient of 0.2211. This means that if the GCG value increases by one unit and the other independent variables remain constant, the GCG ratio is predicted to decrease by 0.2211 units.
4. The value of ROA has a regression coefficient of 0.2475. This means that if the ROA value increases by one unit and the other independent variables remain constant, the ROA ratio is predicted to decrease by 0.2475 units.
5. The value of CAR has a regression coefficient of 0.0281. This means that if the CAR value increases by one unit and the other independent variables remain constant, the CAR ratio is predicted to increase by 0.0281 units.

B. Hypothesis Testing

1. F-Statistic Test

The F-test is employed to evaluate the overall feasibility of the regression model prior to hypothesis testing. The results of the F-statistic test are presented in Table 2 below:

Table 2. Results of the F-Statistic Test

R-squared	0.184065	Mean dependent var	0.939796
Adjusted R-squared	0.164042	S.D. dependent var	2.065762
S.E. of regression	1.888742	Sum squared resid	581.4772
F-statistic	9.192694	Durbin-Watson stat	1.765738
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000001		

Based on the table, the Prob(F-statistic) value is 0.000001, which is less than 0.05. This indicates that the regression model is statistically significant and appropriate for use in this study.

2. Hypothesis Testing (t-test)

Based on Table 1, it can be seen that:

1. The probability value of NPL is 0.0274, which is less than 0.05, indicating that the hypothesis is accepted. This result implies that the risk profile variable, proxied by non-performing loans, has a significant negative effect on firm value.
2. The probability value of GCG is 0.6468, which exceeds 0.05, indicating that the hypothesis is rejected. This finding suggests that good corporate governance, proxied by self-assessment, does not have a significant effect on firm value.
3. The probability value of ROA is 0.0003, which is less than 0.05, indicating that the hypothesis is accepted but with an opposite direction of relationship. This result indicates that the earnings variable, proxied by return on assets, has a significant negative effect on firm value.
4. The probability value of CAR is 0.0000, which is less than 0.05, indicating that the hypothesis is accepted. This finding demonstrates that the capital variable, proxied by the capital adequacy ratio, has a significant positive effect on firm value.

C. Determination Coefficient Test

Based on Table 2, the adjusted R-squared value is 0.1640, or 16.4%, indicating that the risk profile (NPL), good corporate governance (self-assessment), earnings (ROA), and capital (CAR) variables jointly explain 16.4% of the variation in firm value. The remaining 83.6% is attributed to other factors not included in this research model.

E. Discussion

1. Effect of Risk Profile on Firm Value

The results of the first hypothesis test indicate that the risk profile, proxied by non-performing loans (NPL), has a significant negative effect on firm value. This finding suggests that an increase in the NPL ratio reflects higher credit risk faced by banks, which ultimately reduces firm value. Conversely, a decline in NPL indicates an improvement in credit quality that can enhance firm value. This result is consistent with banking risk management theory, which posits that higher NPL levels increase the potential for losses arising from problem loans and place downward pressure on banks’ financial performance.

Moreover, this finding supports Signaling Theory, whereby the NPL ratio serves as a signal to investors regarding asset quality and a bank’s ability to manage credit risk. A high NPL ratio is perceived as negative information (bad news) because it indicates deteriorating credit quality and an increased likelihood of default, which ultimately undermines investor confidence and reduces firm value. From an operational perspective, an elevated risk profile reflected in high NPL levels may disrupt banks’ operational stability and liquidity due to constrained cash flows from principal and interest repayments. Such conditions may lead to lower profitability, which is subsequently reflected in declining stock prices and firm value.

The results of this study are consistent with prior research by Adyaksana et al. (2024), Apriyanti et al. (2023), and Prabawati et al. (2021), which report that risk profile (NPL) has a significant negative effect on firm value. However, these findings contrast with Anisa & Suryandari (2021), who find a significant positive effect of NPL on firm value, and differ from several other studies that conclude NPL has no significant effect on firm value (Salsabila et al., 2024; Haq et al., 2022; Aprilia & Hapsari, 2021; Ilham et al., 2020; Ristiani & Santoso, 2018).

2. Effect of Good Corporate Governance on Firm Value

The results of the second hypothesis test indicate that good corporate governance (GCG), proxied by self-assessment, does not have a significant effect on firm value. This finding suggests that variations in GCG implementation as measured through self-assessment are not sufficient to explain changes in firm value. The result is inconsistent with corporate governance theory, which posits that lower GCG self-assessment scores indicate higher governance quality, thereby enhancing investor confidence and increasing firm value. Accordingly, this finding also fails to support Signaling Theory, under which effective GCG implementation should serve as positive information (good news) for investors and other stakeholders.

According to Apriyanti et al. (2023), effective corporate governance practices are expected to improve investor and creditor protection, which ultimately contributes positively to firm value. However, the empirical evidence in this study indicates that GCG assessment through a self-assessment mechanism does not exert a direct and significant influence on firm value. This outcome may be attributed to the fact that most banks had already implemented relatively sound governance practices prior to the self-assessment process, causing variations in GCG scores to be largely administrative in nature and reflective of regulatory compliance rather than a differentiating factor that shapes market perceptions (Lestari et al., 2022).

These findings are consistent with Lestari et al. (2022), who report that GCG (self-assessment) has a negative but insignificant effect on firm value. In addition, the results support the conclusions of Salsabila et al. (2024),

Adyaksana et al. (2024), Haq et al. (2022), and Anisa & Suryandari (2021), all of whom find that GCG (self-assessment) does not have a significant effect on firm value. In contrast, this study’s findings differ from those of Apriyanti et al. (2023), who document a positive and significant effect of GCG on firm value, as well as Ristiani & Santoso (2018), who report a significant negative relationship.

3. Effect of Earnings on Firm Value

The results of the third hypothesis test reveal that earnings, proxied by return on assets (ROA), have a significant negative effect on firm value. This finding indicates that an increase in ROA is associated with a decline in firm value. The result is inconsistent with profitability theory, which posits that a higher ROA reflects more efficient asset utilization in generating profits and should therefore enhance investor interest and firm value. Accordingly, this finding also fails to support Signaling Theory, under which a high ROA is generally perceived as positive information (good news) regarding a firm’s performance and future prospects.

Previous studies, such as Salsabila et al. (2024), argue that an increase in ROA reflects improved efficiency and higher profitability, which can lead to an increase in firm value. However, the empirical evidence in this study suggests that, within the banking industry context, a high ROA may be interpreted as negative information (bad news), particularly when it is not accompanied by asset growth and long-term expansion. A high ROA may signal limited reinvestment of profits into productive assets, leading banks to be perceived as less aggressive in pursuing growth strategies. Such perceptions may reduce investor interest in bank stocks and consequently lower firm value. This interpretation is consistent with the arguments of Fauziah & Kadarningsih (2023) and Handayani et al. (2023), who suggest that excessively high ROA may reflect insufficient profit reinvestment and exert a negative influence on firm value.

The findings of this study are consistent with those of Fauziah & Kadarningsih (2023) and Handayani et al. (2023), who conclude that ROA has a significant negative effect on firm value, and align with Aprilia & Hapsari (2021), who document an effect of ROA on firm value. In contrast, these results differ from those of Salsabila et al. (2024), Adyaksana et al. (2024), and Prabawati et al. (2021), who report a positive and significant relationship between ROA and firm value, and do not support studies that find no significant effect of ROA on firm value (Apriyanti et al., 2023; Haq et al., 2022; Anisa & Suryandari, 2021; Anggarsini & Suprasto, 2018).

4. Effect of Capital on Firm Value

The results of the fourth hypothesis test indicate that capital, proxied by the Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR), has a positive and significant effect on firm value. This finding suggests that an improvement in capital adequacy

contributes to an increase in firm value. The result is consistent with banking theory, which posits that a higher CAR strengthens a bank’s capacity to absorb potential losses and reduces the likelihood of financial distress, thereby enhancing investor and depositor confidence. This finding also supports Signaling Theory, whereby a high level of capital adequacy serves as positive information (good news) for investors and other stakeholders regarding a bank’s financial stability and its ability to sustain operational activities.

Anisa & Suryandari (2021) argue that an increase in CAR reflects a bank’s ability to finance risk-weighted assets and strengthen its business prospects, which ultimately leads to higher firm value. Accordingly, banks with higher CAR levels are perceived as having more robust capital structures to withstand risk, signaling more favorable future prospects. Such conditions encourage greater investor interest, rising stock prices, and ultimately a positive impact on firm value. The findings of this study are consistent with those of Adyaksana et al. (2024), Apriyanti et al. (2023), Prabawati et al. (2021), and Anisa & Suryandari (2021), all of whom report that CAR has a positive and significant effect on firm value. However, these results contrast with the findings of Refrayadi & Kufepaksi (2024), who document a negative effect of CAR on firm value, and differ from the results of Salsabila et al. (2024), Haq et al. (2022), and Ristiani & Santoso (2018), which conclude that CAR does not have a significant effect on firm value.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the research results and discussion in the previous chapter, the conclusions obtained from this research are:

1. Risk profile, proxied by non-performing loans (NPL), has a significant negative effect on firm value. This result indicates that a higher NPL ratio increases the risk of losses arising from problem loans, thereby reducing investor confidence and firm value.
2. Good corporate governance, proxied by self-assessment, has a negative but insignificant effect on firm value. This finding suggests that the implementation of GCG through self-assessment has not yet produced a direct impact on enhancing firm value.
3. Earnings, proxied by return on assets (ROA), have a significant negative effect on firm value. This result implies that a high ROA is perceived as negative information (bad news), which may arise from differing investor interpretations of high profitability and can adversely influence their perceptions, thereby reducing investment interest and lowering firm value.
4. Capital, proxied by the capital adequacy ratio (CAR), has a significant positive effect on firm

value. This finding indicates that a higher CAR strengthens banks’ capital positions in managing risk and reducing the likelihood of financial distress, thereby enhancing investor confidence and increasing firm value.

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